

Biuret Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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The preparations of anionic complexes of biuret with Cu(II) and Ni(II) in alkaline media, stabilized by counter cations, Na⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Tl⁺ are described. The complexes are characterized by magnetic susceptibility, electronic, infrared and EPR spectral measurements and thermal studies. The results indicate the bonding of deprotonated amido nitrogen to the metal with square planar arrangement. The final products of decomposition of the complexes around 400° are mixtures of transition metal(II) oxide and alkali or alkaline earth metal carbonates or thallium(III) oxide.

BIURET (H₂NCONHCONH₂) is known to form¹⁻³ *O*-coordinated and *N*-coordinated six membered chelates with Cu(II) and Zn(II). It also behaves⁴ as a monodenate ligand in dichlorobis(biuret) cadmium(II). Till recently studies on the interaction of metal salts with biuret were carried out mainly in solution⁵. McLellan and Melson^{6,7} have prepared several transition metal complexes with biuret and have established the mode of bonding in then by spectral measurements. Nakamoto *et al*⁸ have carried out detail normal coordinate analyses on metal-biuret complexes and assigned the observed bands. We report in this paper the isolation of anionic biuret complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) in alkaline media stabilized by counter cations, Na⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Tl⁺. The complexes are characterized by thermogravimetric analysis and magnetic susceptibility, electronic, infrared and EPR spectral measurements.

Experimental

Materials :

Biuret was obtained from BDH, London and was used without further purification. All other chemicals were obtained commercially and were of reagent grade or equivalent.

Preparation of the complexes :

(1) *Sodium bis(biureto)cuprate(II) tetrahydrate* : Cupric acetate monohydrate (0.01 mole, 1.99 g) and biuret (0.02 mole, 2.06 g) were dissolved in 30 ml of 10M NaOH. The clear solution was kept aside for 2-3 days. The crystallized red-violet compound was separated, washed with methanol and dried in a desiccator.

(2) *Sodium bis(biureto)nickelate(II) dihydrate* : Nickel acetate tetrahydrate (0.01 mole, 2.49 g) dissolved in 30 ml of 12M NaOH. The stirred solution

was filtered and the clear filtrate was left standing for 3-4 days. The separated yellow crystals were filtered, washed with methanol and dried in a desiccator.

(3) *Barium bis(biureto)cuprate(II) dihydrate* : This complex was prepared by dissolving cupric acetate monohydrate (0.01 mole, 1.99 g) and biuret (0.02 mole, 2.06 g) in 40 ml of 8M KOH. To the clear solution, 1M barium nitrate solution was added till no more violet precipitate formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and acetone and dried.

(4) *Barium bis(biureto)nickelate(II) dihydrate* : Nickel acetate tetrahydrate (0.01 mole, 2.49 g) and biuret (0.02 mole, 2.06 g) were dissolved in minimum amount of water and to it was added 30 ml of 8M KOH. The yellow solution obtained was filtered, washed with water and acetone and dried.

(5) *Strontium bis(biureto)cuprate(II) dihydrate*.

(6) *Strontium bis(biureto)nickelate(II) dihydrate*.

(7) *Thallium bis(biureto)cuprate(II)*
and

(8) *Thallium bis(biureto)nickelate(II)*.

These were prepared by the same methods as (3) and (4) except 1M solutions of strontium nitrate and thallium(I) nitrate were employed instead of 1M barium nitrate.

Analytical :

Nickel was determined by precipitating as dimethylglyoximate and copper by iodometrically after removing the organic moiety by decomposing the complexes. Barium and strontium were determined by precipitating as the respective sulphates. Sodium was determined by heating the complexes to 400° and treating the products (Na₂CO₃ and MO) in water

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and titrating Na_2CO_3 with standard acid. Thallium was determined by bromine-DMSO method⁹, nickel does not interfere. When thallium and copper were present together copper was removed first by electrolysis. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. The analytical values of the complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF METAL-BIURET COMPLEXES

Complex	N (%)	Cu/Ni (%)	Na/Ba/Sr/Tl (%)
1. $\text{Na}_2\text{Cubi}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	F 21.32	16.13	11.24
	C 21.80	16.56	11.98
2. $\text{Na}_2\text{Nibi}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	F 24.31	18.21	12.76
	C 23.92	17.06	13.37
3. $\text{BaCubi}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	F 18.96	28.96	30.84
	C 19.52	28.71	31.24
4. $\text{BaNibi}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	F 19.41	13.97	31.72
	C 19.29	13.49	31.55
5. $\text{SrCubi}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	F 21.36	17.28	21.98
	C 21.08	17.65	22.44
6. $\text{SrNibi}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	F 22.45	15.15	22.34
	C 21.84	15.22	22.72
7. Tl_2Cubi_2	F 11.96	8.49	59.86
	C 12.48	8.93	60.49
8. Tl_2Nibi_2	F 12.24	8.42	60.41
	C 12.71	8.30	60.93

bi = $(\text{HNCONHCONH})_2^-$, F = Found, C = Calculated.

Physical measurements :

Magnetic measurements were made at room temperature by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_4$ Co as the magnetic standard. The susceptibilities of the ligands were calculated from Pascal's constants¹⁰. Electronic spectra were obtained with Carl Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer. The spectra of the solid complexes were taken by employing nujol mull on filter paper technique. Infrared absorption spectra were measured by using Perkin Elmer 237 spectrophotometer in the range $4000-625\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Beckman IR-12 spectrometer in the range $650-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Both nujol mull and KBr techniques were used. EPR spectra of the powdered samples of copper complexes were obtained at room temperature in Varian E-4 X-band spectrometer using DPPH as the standard.

Thermogravimetric studies were made in air using recording Stanton thermobalance with a continuous heating rate of 6° per min.

Results and Discussion

The cuprate(II) complexes are violet-red in colour whereas the nickelate(II) complexes are yellow in colour. Sodium biuretometallates(II) are soluble in water, other complexes are insoluble in water as well as in common organic solvents. Barium and strontium complexes on suspension in water slowly precipitate the respective carbonates and thallium(II) complexes are found to gradually decolourise with time. In acidic solutions the complexes dissociate to give the corresponding metal salts.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENTS, ELECTRONIC AND EPR SPECTRAL DATA OF METAL-BIURET COMPLEXES

Complex	Magnetic moment $\mu_{eff}(\text{B.M.})$	Electronic spectra (kK)	EPR spectra	
			g_{11}	g_1
1	1.78	20.6	2.141	2.055
2	diamag.	24.4	—	—
3	1.81	21.3	2.063	—
4	diamag.	23.5	—	—
5	1.86	21.3	2.095	—
6	diamag.	23.3	—	—
7	1.88	21.2	2.156	2.063
8	diamag.	24.6	—	—

Magnetic properties :

The magnetic moments (Table 2) of the cuprate(II) complexes are in the range 1.78 to 1.88 B.M. which are close to the 'spin-only' value expected for $3d^9$ Cu(II) with normal magnetic properties¹¹. The nickelate(II) complexes are diamagnetic suggesting square planar structure around Ni(II).

Electronic spectra :

The absorption spectra of nickelate(II) complexes have the band maxima around 24 kK which is characteristic of square planar nickel(II). Similar absorption band at 22kK is noticed¹² for potassium bis(biureto)nickelate(II) in which Ni(II) is definitely in planar arrangement. The spectrum of the solid is very similar to that found for an aqueous solution of Na_2Nibi_2 indicating the water molecules have negligible effect on the structure of the complex. The absorption band maxima for the solid cuprate(II) complexes appear at 21 kK which is characteristic of square planar coordination¹³ around copper(II). This absorption maximum has slightly shifted to lower frequency region, 19.8 kK in Na_2Cubi_2 . The solution spectra of sodium cuprate(II) and nickelate(II) complexes have a strong absorption around 35 kK which is associated with the ligand.

Infrared spectra :

The principal infrared absorption bands have been listed in Table 3 and the assignments were made based on the work of Nakamoto *et al*¹⁴ on K_2Cubi_2

TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF BIURET-METAL COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Assignment
3450	3510 3450	3400	3500	3400	3400	—	—	$\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$
3345	3350	3360	3358	3350	3340	3390	3320	$\nu(\text{NH})$ amido
3310	3320	3320	3310	3320	3290	3270	3300	
3170	3170	3170	3190	3185	3180	3185	3180	$\nu(\text{NH})$ imido
1658	1650	1645	1650	1650	1650	1650	1650	$\nu(\text{CO})+$
1585	1580	1585	1585	1590	1585	1565	1580	$\nu(\text{CN})$
1612	1635	1635	1600	1640	1600	—	—	$\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$
1430	1430	1445	1445	1455	1460	1420	1420	$\nu(\text{CN})$
1360	1385	1335	1370	1370	1365	1365	1365	
973	990	975	998	955	1000	—	1005	
420	470	425	440	475	455	460	452	$\nu(\text{M-N})+$
355	355	355	350	350	355	358	350	$\delta(\text{CO})$
270	268	275	280	265	295	280	280	$\nu(\text{M-N})+$ ring def.

$2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The spectra of the complexes look quite similar and resemble that of potassium analogue. As the complexes are isolated from alkaline solutions it is expected that they are all *N*-bonded. This is evident from the shifting of NH_2 stretching frequency observed at 3400 cm^{-1} in free biuret to 3300 cm^{-1} to the metal atom. The bands in the region $1700\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed for biuret are associated with CO stretching and NH_2 bending modes. These are not much affected in their positions due to complexation suggesting only intermolecular hydrogen bonding and no *O*-coordination to the metal. The additional frequencies observed for the hydrated complexes around 3400 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} are assigned to stretching and bending modes respectively of non-bonded water. The strong band observed at 3200 cm^{-1} in biuret is not changed significantly in the complexes suggesting it is due to imido NH stretching which does not involve in bonding to the metal. The bands around 450 , 350 and 270 cm^{-1} involve metal-nitrogen stretching components in the metal-biuret complexes⁸. Thus the metal atoms are surrounded by four *N* atoms of the amido NH groups in a square planar arrangement.

EPR spectra :

The EPR spectra of sodium and thallium(I), cuprate(II) have both g_{11} and g_1 values whereas the corresponding barium and strontium cuprates(II) have only one g values. In a completely isotropic case only one characteristic g value is noticed but when there is anisotropy with axial symmetry, in a powdered sample the g value is split and g_{11} and g_1 are obtained. Proctor, Hathaway and Nicholls¹⁴ have postulated that when the ratio $(g_{11}-2)/(g_1-2)$ is greater than four the exchange interaction is

negligible and when it is less than four then considerable exchange interaction is present. The calculated ratios are 2.62 (Na^+) and 2.48 (Tl^+) which suggest that the interactions are present in these complexes. But this interaction must be very weak as the magnetic moments of these complexes are normal. Magnetic measurements below room temperature may throw some light on this aspect.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

In the case of hydrated complexes the decomposition takes place in two stages (Table 4). The first stage of decomposition sets in around 120° and is

TABLE 4—THERMAL DECOMPOSITION DATA OF METAL-BIURET COMPLEXES

Compound	Weight loss %			
	I Stage (dehydration)		II Stage (Formation of $\text{M}_1\text{CO}_3 + \text{M}_2\text{O}$)	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1	12.0	11.8	48.0	48.4
2	10.2	10.5	44.0	45.9
3	8.0	8.2	37.2	37.9
4	8.0	8.3	36.5	37.3
5	9.0	9.3	41.0	41.7
6	9.0	9.4	41.0	40.9
7	—	—	19.0	20.5*
8	—	—	19.0	20.6*

$\text{M}_1 = 2\text{Na}$, Ba or Sr ; $\text{M}_2 = \text{Cu}$ or Ni

* End product $\text{M}_2\text{O} + \text{Tl}_2\text{O}_3$.

complete by 160°, the weight loss corresponds to the removal of water of hydration from the complexes. The anhydrous complexes decompose around 200° and is complete by 400°. The final products are analysed and are found to be alkali and alkaline-earth metal carbonates and copper(II) or nickel(II) oxides, which is confirmed by the observed weight loss. Thallium(II) complexes start decomposing around 220° and the decomposition is complete by 400°. The final decomposition products were analysed to be a mixture of thallium(III) oxide and copper (II) or nickel(II) oxides. The weight loss recorded also confirmed this observation.

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